

Effect of Ultraviolet Light on Enzymatic Reactions.

Part I. Diastase.

BY SOBHANLAL BANERJEE AND H. K. SEN.

While studying the decomposition of α -keto-carboxylic acids by organic catalysts, it was noticed that in certain instances when the decomposition was effected in the presence of ultraviolet light, the catalysts suffered a perceptible diminution in their activity. Thus in the presence of ultraviolet light, gelatine, egg-albumin, and urea suffered diminution in their catalytic power of decomposing pyruvic acid, whereas catalysts like phenylaminoacetic acid, asparagine, activated charcoal, platinum, etc., retained their usual activity. If natural enzymes be provisionally regarded as highly complex bodies, nitrogenous or otherwise, it may be inferred similarly that the ultraviolet light would cause a destruction or retrogression of their usual activity. This is usually the case. There appeared, however, the possibility of stopping such destruction by the use of accelerators, the assumption being that the rate of inhibition by the ultraviolet falls short of the rate of acceleration by the accelerators. Viewed differently, the accelerators may in fact serve as filters against the ultraviolet. Although, separately, an accelerator solution may act as a filter, in a solution with the substrate and the enzyme, the reaction of the ultraviolet may be considered more of a selective nature, the accelerators being more sensitive to the light thrust. With phenylaminoacetic acid, etc., the activation of the carboxylase reaction of yeast is definite, and a further attempt was made to increase the catalytic action by ultraviolet light treatment. The result was destructive. With diastase, however, the result was different. Ordinarily, the diastatic ferment in malt is known to be completely rendered inactive by the ultraviolet light (*cf.* Pincussen, *Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 134, 459; 1924, 144, 366; 1924, 152, 406, 416). The protective action of some salts, with special reference to the degree of protection rendered by particular kations, was also investigated by his school (Pincussen and Kumanomidoh, *Biochem. Z.*, 1928, 195, 79). Thus, potassium chloride offers less protection than magnesium chloride,

which again was less effective than calcium chloride. The explanation suggested by him relates to the probable coarsening of the enzyme particles by the action of the ultraviolet light. This analogy is derived from the known capacity of such light to effect a coarsening in the colloidal system. Considering the enzyme as a dual complex between a colloidal member and another active portion, the *acceptor*, adsorbed on the colloid, a change in the dispersion of the colloid of the enzyme by the action of the ultraviolet light would, in all probability, inhibit its activity. In fact, a retardation in the velocity of enzyme action does take place. The addition of salts would also cause a change in the dispersion grade of the enzyme, but if this change is such that the light cannot affect the enzyme any more then a certain amount of protection would be exercised by the salt. It is further known that potassium salts change the dispersion less than calcium, *i.e.*, the dispersed particles are rendered coarser by the latter, and hence less susceptible to the action of light. From the experimental data of Pincussen, this protection by salts appears to be of a very moderate order, but in our case, with phenylaminoacetic acid, etc., the protection is substantially marked. It is not known that these amino acids have any action similar to those of salts. It seems, therefore, that amino acids act as protective agents for different reasons, which may be provisionally regarded as of the nature of a light screen. We could not confirm Pincussen's statement in this connection that the activity of an enzyme can be revived if a minute amount of fresh enzyme is added to the illuminated system (*Fermentforschung*, 1925, 8, 181). Nor can we at this stage definitely state that purified enzymes are most sensitive to the action of light (*loc. cit.*). In the present case, purified malt diastase was used, whilst in Pincussen's experiments, pancreatic diastase was taken for this portion of the work. Mention may further be made of the protective action of dyestuff (Claus, *Biochem. Z.*, 1929, 204, 456; Pincussen and Kambayashi, *ibid.*, 1928, 203, 334), but it has no particular bearing on our present work. It was observed in course of this work that the several amines, amino acids and ammonium salts etc., not only increase the activity of the diastase itself, but also protect the enzyme from complete destruction by the action of the ultraviolet rays, the activity of the enzyme, however, being appreciably minimised. Such destructive property of the ultraviolet light in therapy is very significant, but the discovery of protective reagents would be no less

important, as the latter would no doubt increase the flexibility in the employment of such light in actino-therapeutic science. Accordingly, four sets of experiments were performed with malt diastase: (i) without catalyst, (ii) with catalyst, (iii) with catalyst and ultraviolet light, (iv) without catalyst and with ultraviolet light. The following table gives the results of such experiments. It will be noticed that the diastatic values given under column 3, are not the same. The reason for this is the difference in strength of the diastase solution which was freshly prepared for each set of experiments.

TABLE I.

1 C.c. of 0.1% soln. of catalyst used.

Catalyst.	Control expt. Diastatic value. D ₁	With catalyst. Diastatic value. D ₂	With catalyst & ultraviolet. Diastatic value. D ₃	Control expt. Without catalyst with ultraviolet. Diastatic value. D ₄	Constant p ^H value.
Asparagine	18.5	31.8	Nil (15 mins.)	Nil (45 mins.)	5.6
Phenylaminoacetic acid	31.8	48.5	8.5 ..	Nil ..	5.6
Asparagine	23.5	31.8	9.6 (5 mins.)	Nil	5.6
Gelatine	23.5	23.5	15.16 ..	Nil (5 mins.)	5.4
Gelatine	31.8	31.8	9.6 (45 mins.)	Nil (45 mins.)	5.6
Egg-albumin	31.8	31.8	Nil ..	Nil ..	5.6
Glutamic acid	31.8	31.8	Nil ..	Nil ..	5.4
Leucine	23.5	23.5	Nil ..	Nil ..	5.4
Tyrosine	48.5	48.5	9.6 ..	Nil ..	5.4
Aminobenzoic acid	23.5	31.8	9.6 ..	Nil ..	5.6
Ammonium tartrate	23.5	31.8	Nil ..	Nil ..	5.4
Ammonium oxalate	18.5	23.5	Nil ..	Nil ..	5.6
Ammonium benzoate	31.8	31.8	Nil ..	Nil ..	5.6
Ammonium formate	18.5	18.5	Nil (45 mins.)	Nil (45 mins.)	5.6
Ammonium citrate	23.5	31.8	Do	Do	5.8
Do	23.5	31.8	Nil (10 mins.)	Nil (10 mins.)	5.6
Do	18.5	23.5	11 (5)		5.6
Ammonium chloride	23.5	23.5	Nil (10)	Nil (10 mins.)	5.4
Ammonium bromide	18.5	18.5	Do	Do	5.4
Microcosmic salt	23.5	23.5	Do	Do	5.6
Urea	23.5	23.5	Nil (45 mins.)	Nil (45 mins.)	5.6
Phenylurea	31.8	31.8	Do	Do	5.6
Thiourea	23.5	23.5	Do	Do	5.6

It would appear from the previous table that asparagine, phenylaminoacetic acid, ammonium citrate, gelatine, tyrosine, aminobenzoic acid etc., cause varying degrees of increment of diastatic activity and exert protective action on malt diastase against the ultraviolet light. Thus, an exposure of 5 minutes to the ultraviolet light (3000 C. P., 12" arc) at a distance of 2' was just sufficient to completely destroy the diastatic activity of a sample of malt. If gelatine was added during the reaction, and the whole was exposed to the ultraviolet for 5 minutes only as in the previous case, the diastatic power, though reduced, was still found to be 15.16—and when exposed for 45 minutes the diastatic value was 9.6. On the other hand, for the same period of 5 minutes, ammonium citrate under identical conditions, gives the diastatic value 11. This shows that the protective action of gelatine is greater than that of ammonium citrate. It is obvious that a distinction must be drawn between an accelerator and a protector. But it is quite possible that certain substances function as both. For example, phenylaminoacetic acid, tyrosin, aminobenzoic acid, ammonium citrate are both accelerators and protectors. Whilst from the chemical nature of the accelerators, a surmise may be drawn as to the nature of the diastatic fraction of the malt, the protective action probably depends upon the capacity to absorb partially or wholly the destructive wave-lengths of the ultraviolet light. Expressed in a slightly different way, the light acts selectively on these protectors leaving the diastatic enzyme wholly or partially active. This appears plausible when we consider that gelatine, ammonium citrate and, in fact, many albuminoid substances are affected by the ultraviolet light.

Procedure.—The diastase used in the present investigation was prepared in the usual way, by steeping barley in water and then allowing the grains to germinate in a warm place until the plumules were 1/2 inch in length. The dry malt was then extracted with two to four parts of 20% alcohol for 24 hours. The solution was filtered and precipitated with 2 to 2.5 parts of absolute alcohol, treated with ether and dried in *vacuo*. The preparation was redissolved in water, then reprecipitated and dialysed. In these experiments, 0.15 to 0.2 g. of the dry diastase was dissolved in 100 c. c. of water and filtered before use.

The diastatic value was determined by the Lintner method. In each of a series of ten clean and numbered test tubes of approximately the same bore, is placed the same quantity of soluble starch solution

(usually 10 c.c. of 2% soln.) and then a progressively increasing quantity of the diastase extract, *i.e.*, 0.1 c.c. in No. 1 tube, 0.2 c.c. in No. 2, 0.3 c.c. in No. 3 and so on. The contents are mixed and placed in a bath kept constant near about the room temperature for exactly one hour 5 C.c. of Fehling's solution are now added in each tube as quickly as possible and the tubes are now heated in a boiling water-bath for 20 minutes and then examined. Some of the tubes in the series will show no blue colour, or are faintly yellow, whilst others are still blue. The amount of enzyme in the first colourless tube is that amount which will just convert the fixed amount of starch into maltose in the given time.

The diastatic power is based upon 0.1 c.c. of the enzyme solution and called 100.

Therefore, if the result was between the 6th and 7th tube, the diastatic power $D = \frac{100 \times 0.1}{0.65} = 15.4$.

Before adding the enzyme into starch solution, the p_H of the latter was determined colorimetrically, with and without the solution of the so-called activator. The p_H of the solutions was kept always constant (for the same set of experiments) either by the addition of $N/100$ -NaOH or $N/100$ -HCl to the starch solution in which the solution of the catalyst has been added and making neutral to Wisslow's indicator (mixture of methyl red and methyl blue). This was necessary to show that the effect of the activators is not due to a more favourable hydrogen ion concentration induced by their presence (amino acids etc. *cf.* Sherman and Thomas, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1960; 1921, 43, 2461). The catalyst added was usually 1 c.c. of its 0.1 % solution.

The experiments with ultraviolet light were carried out in quartz tubes. The mercury vapour lamp used was of 3000 C. P.—with an arc of 12" and it was placed at a distance of two feet from the tubes meant for exposure.